

Comparative study of teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 year integrated B.Ed. Programme

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Abstract

Teachers play a vital role in student's life. They act as mentors, friend, philosophers and guide. If the teachers have updated knowledge and understanding then they are the ones who can bring positive changes in the society. With regard to this the researcher chooses few areas which are necessary to be thorough, for the teacher trainees. Hence the researcher develops self-constructed tool to access the level of knowledge gained in the areas of ICT, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills and awareness of acquisition of Bloom's taxonomy. The data is collected and analyzed using t-test.

Key words: ICT, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills and awareness of acquisition of Bloom's taxonomy

Introduction

Education is the dynamic side of philosophy. It is the active aspect and the practical means of realizing the ideas of life. Education is necessity of life, both from biological and sociological point of view. It is undeniably true that education works like a catalyst for a better life, a social desirable life. Education renews and rebuilds the social structure on the pattern of philosophical ideas. Education according to Indian tradition is not merely a means to earn the livelihood, nor is it only a nursery of thought or a school for citizenship. It is rather the initiation into the life of spirit, a training of human source in pursuit of truth and the practice of virtue.

The task of building enlightened, strong and prosperous nation rests on the shoulders of its children who are to be cherished, nurtured and developed with tenderness and care. Education as always played this important role and has there by emerged as a natural characteristic of human societies. It has contributed to the shaping of the destinies of the societies in all phases of their development and it has never ceased to develop. It has been torch bearer of humanity's most noble ideas.

Education has been recognized as a fundamental right and it is viewed as a process of human resource development where the knowledge, skills and capabilities are sharpened to achieve a wide range of objectives.

Statement of Problem

In the present study, the researcher has tried to compare 2 year and 4 year integrated B.Ed. programme with respect to ICT awareness, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills and acquisition of Bloom’s Taxonomy by teacher trainees with the help of self-constructed tool.

Objective

To compare awareness of teachers trainee studying in 2 year and 4 year integrated B.Ed. programme with respect to ICT awareness, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills and acquisition of Bloom’s Taxonomy.

Research Methodology

The data is collected by sending structured questionnaire to the teachers trainees studying in different colleges in of Gujarat state 2 year and 4 year integrated B.Ed. Programme.

Independent sample ‘t test’ is used to analyse the data.

Hypothesis Testing & Interpretation

As per the collected data out of 477 total respondents 239 respondents belongs to 2 years B.Ed. Programme while 238 respondents belongs to integrated B.Ed. Programme. Here to compare the awareness for various parameters researches has tries to collect equal respondents from both type of programme.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between ICT awareness of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Table 1: Comparison of mean score of ICT awareness between trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme

Course	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	t	Remark
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2 Years	239	1.59	.269	.0174	.132	Accepted
4 Years	238	1.56	.245	.0158		

As t value between 2 years B.Ed. Programme and 4 years integrated B.Ed. programme is 0.132 which is greater than 0.05, null hypothesis is accepted which means there is no significant difference between ICT awareness of B.Ed. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.Ed. programme.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between awareness of acquisition of cognitive domain of Bloom’s taxonomy of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Table 2: Comparison of mean score of awareness about Bloom’s taxonomy between trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. Programme

Course	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	T	Remark
2 Years	239	1.56	.178	.0115	.000	Rejected
4 Years	238	1.66	.212	.0137		

As t value between 2 years B.Ed. Programme and 4 years integrated B.Ed. programme is 0.000 which is less than 0.05, null hypothesis is rejected which means there is a significant difference between awareness of acquisition of cognitive domain of Bloom's taxonomy of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Ho3: There is no significant difference between emotional maturity of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Table 3: Comparison of mean score of emotional maturity of trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. Programme

Course	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	t	Remark
2 Years	239	2.95	.331	.0214	.110	Accepted
4 Years	238	2.98	.289	.0187		

As t value between 2 years B.Ed. Programme and 4 years integrated B.Ed. programme is 0.110 which is greater than 0.05, null hypothesis is accepted which means there is no significant difference between emotional maturity of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Ho4: There is no significant difference between Interpersonal skills of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Table 4: Comparison of mean score of Interpersonal skills of trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. Programme

Course	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	t	Remark
2 Years	239	2.96	.334	.0216	.394	Accepted
4 Years	238	2.99	.351	.0227		

As t value between 2 years B.Ed. Programme and 4 years integrated B.Ed. programme is 0.394 which is greater than 0.05, null hypothesis is accepted which means there is no significant difference between Interpersonal skills of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

Findings

As per the statistical results only Ho2 is rejected and others are accepted. As Blooms taxonomy is cognitive domain of the B.ED programme, the trainee whether opts for 2 years or 4 years programme, they have to be updated for the same and it requires depth study therefore it is more in trainees studying in 4 Year integrated B.ED. Programme which proves that there is a significant difference between awareness of acquisition of cognitive domain of Bloom’s taxonomy of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

The results shows that irrespective of course duration which is 2 years and 4 years all the B.ED teaches trainees are fully aware about the ICT, As its a modern era and all are techno friendly and technical awareness is very easy to grab, therefore there is no significance difference between ICT awareness of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

The results shows that irrespective of course duration which is 2 years and 4 years all the B.ED teaches trainees have similar emotional maturity because ultimately they are going to have teaching practice at various stages and they are future teachers who will be dealing with children therefore requirement of emotional maturity is must and therefore there is no significant difference between emotional maturity of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. programme.

The results shows that irrespective of course duration which is 2 years and 4 years all the B.ED teaches trainees have to develop the Interpersonal skills and it is inbuilt which has to be enhanced therefore whether the person is studying in 2 years or 4 years, interpersonal skills like humanity, leadership, polite speaking, convincing skills, etc has to be developed during the course therefore there is no significant difference between Interpersonal skills of B.ED. teacher trainees studying in 2 year and 4 Year integrated B.ED. Programme.

Conclusion

It is concluded that B.ED teachers trainee has to be aware about ICT awareness, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills and acquisition of Bloom's Taxonomy. It is observed that whether they belong to 2 years programme or 4 years integrated programme there is no significance difference between ICT awareness, Emotional maturity, Interpersonal skills as these are the skills are not relevant with duration of course rather teacher has to develop this and few skills can be develop while learning after entering into teaching profession one can improve it.

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